

Folk Elements in The Sculptures of DattāTreya MahāDeva Temple at Dattnagar, Shimla District of Himachal Pradesh

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Abstract

The term 'folk' describes the common people of a society or particular region considered as the representative of a traditional way of life especially the carriers of the socio-religious customs and cultural practices of common people. It is also an emotional outcome of rural people's daily lifestyle. Art forms in Himachal Pradesh have been exquisite and attractive. It has had cultural influences as well as religious impacts. Himachal Pradesh has a rich heritage of regional culture. This is a mixture of multiple cultural traits originating from different sources. On the basis of field visit to the Shimla region of Sutlej valley of Himachal Pradesh, we have noticed an abundance of sculpture belonging from different phases of art forms; therefore, a study of the sculptures of the Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple at Dattnagar of Shimla region of the Sutlej valley is proposed in this study.

Keywords

Mahiṣāsura-mardīnī, Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa, Folk, Shimla Region, Śakti, Ornaments and Dress.

Introduction

There are many studies on many temples of Himachal Pradesh but there are many temples in different districts that deserve much more attention and careful study. The temple is a very important institution. Besides their religious importance it reflects the social-cultural life and various spheres of human activities.[1] One such temple named Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple is discussed in the present study. This temple possessed many stone and metal sculpture which are iconographically very interesting. In the Shimla region of Himachal Pradesh sculptors continue to fashion these sculptures which still serve the majority of the people in the temples, in processions for religious festivals in shrine. Therefore, we can say that artists, who made sculptures according to clearly defined rules in the text, and their style, developed their creative talent to realizing the figures according to the highest standard of which they were capable of. Thus perfection was initially an act of worship.

Objective of study

This paper attempts to analysis the sculpture and their iconographic features of numerous gods and goddesses of brahmanical faith. This paper also brings to light some unpublished images from the imaginative and iconographical perspectives. Therefore, the objective of my study is to shed some light on the peculiar or folk features of the sculptures of the Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple at Dattnagar of Shimla region. We find different unique types of folk or regional elements in sculptures of Dattātreya Mahādeva temple. Regional communities are an integral part of the culture and history of Himachal Pradesh, therefore regional elements influenced much the Himalayan arts and artefacts as we can notice in Indian art.

Review of Literature

Penelope Chetwode in her work, entitled *Kulu: The End of Habitable World* and also in her article 'Traditional Hindu architecture in Western Himalaya', published in

V.C. Ohri's edited book *Arts of Himachal* in 1975, deals with the architecture and sculptures of western Himalaya, especially of the Sutlej Valley.

Mian Govardhan Singh in his work *Wooden Temples of Himachal Pradesh*, (1999) and another work *Art and Architecture of Himachal Pradesh*, (1983) have discussed the temple style and architecture of Himachal Pradesh.

O. C. Handa in his book *Temple Architecture of Western Himalayas: Wooden Temples*, (2001) also referred to some of these temples of the region.

M. Postal, A. Neven, K. Mankodi has published a book entitled *Antiquities of Himachal* in 1985. They have tried to cover all the antiquities of Himachal Pradesh including sculptures but they did not mention all sculptures except some metal sculpture of Shimla region. They throw light on the artistic styles and different trends, which were dominating the sculptures of the Kulu and Sutlej region. Most of these works are exclusively on the temples.

Main Text

Several stray images lying at various places that must have belonged to some temple and some of them are preserved in the museum form a rich repertoire of art. These sculptures prove that culturally Shimla region was active. Recently, a life size sculpture of Viṣṇu is found in the sand mine in Datnagar village that is very similar to the some early sculptures from Nirmand in Kulu region;[2] which indicates the popularity of the image worship in the region dates from very ancient times. Datnagar village derives its name from the temple of Dattātreya. It is situated on the left bank of the Sutlej valley on main National Highway or Hindistan-Tibet-Road. This temple possessed the following sculptures the main sect of Hindu religion:

1. Śaivite
2. Vaiṣṇavite
3. Śakti

Presently, the new temple is under construction. However, in this temple the images of Mahiṣāsūramardīnī are largely outnumber all other. Some carved architectural remains of an old stone temple are seen on the walls of this new structure.

This temple is dedicated to the God Dattātreya. However, here we have copper three separate images (Pl. I) which are completely different from the common representation of god Dattātreya as he is commonly depicted with three-faced in the Hindu pantheons. The centre figure holds a trident in his right hand and an object in his left hand. He also wears a crown and its shape is very different from the other shape of the crown we found in this region. The facial shape and features are very sharp and unique. These sculptures show traits peculiar to the hill region.

The four-handed goddess (Pl. II) stands with one leg planted on the ground and the other rose sideways to press the head of the buffalo demon that she has lifted almost vertically by the tail. A trident held in the right forehand of the Devī is jabbed into the neck of the fallen demonical buffalo. The back right hand holds a raised sword (*khadga*). The other back hand holds a ringing bell (*ghaṅṭikā*). The goddess wears a three-pointed crown set with cockades, *chakra-kunḍala*, bracelets and a girdle with tassels of strings. The beaded necklace forms a loop between the breasts of the Devī. The *āyudhas* are held straight away without adopting any hand poses. Moreover, this image of the goddess seen there seems to belong to the late eighth century, or so.[3] The plastic quantity in the figure of the goddess considered to be the earliest amongst the remains seen here. The sculptures of the middle phase show more characteristics of the Sutlej region and show close similarities with the sculptures of north India.

There is another image (Pl. III) of eight-handed Mahiṣāsūramardīnī standing in *pratiyālīḍha* posture with her right foot on the cushion placed on the back of the buffalo from where the emerging demon brandishing a sword. The goddess grasps the head of the buffalo after the titan by the hair and pooled him with a scimitar raised in the left hand. The goddess jabs at him with a trident, held in her right hand. The other *āyudhas* held by her are clockwise the bell, shield, *khatanga*, head of Mahiṣāsura, trident, noose, bow, and sword. The string necklace supported by a pendant hangs between her breasts; the mount lying is seen biting the hind part of the demon. The image wears *jaṭābhāra*, *keyūra*, *karnakunḍala*, *dhotī*, with *urudhams* and a broad *vaijayantimālā*. She wears *jaṭābhāra* similar to the Lakṣmī and Pārvaṭī as depicted with the god Viṣṇu and Śiva respectively in the other part of Sutlej valley. She also has a pot belly which is very unique. She wears a dress which has studded horizontal stripes generally we find in Nirmand region.[4] The image also shows a halo with lotus petals.

There is also an image (Pl. IV) of Mahiṣāsūramardīnī placed outside the temple. She has eight hands carrying her attributes. Her right four hands are broken; however, we can notice the trident which seems she holds on her right hand. Mahiṣāsūramardīnī standing in *pratiyālīḍha-mudrā* with her right foot placed on the back of the buffalo and the left leg planted on the pedestal. A trident held in the right forehand of the Devī is jabbed into the back of the fallen demonical buffalo. The back right hand holds a raised sword. The other back hand holds a ringing bell. The goddess wears a crown and ornaments such as with *cakra-kunḍalas*, bracelets, anklets and a girdle with tassels of pearl strings. Ornaments worn by the Devī are similar to the earlier discussed sculptures of Mahiṣāsūramardīnī. We can notice the third eye of the goddess on the centre of the forehead.

There is another similar image (Pl. V) of four-handed Mahiṣāsūramardīnī at Dattnagar. It also stands in *pratiyālīḍha* posture with her right foot on the cushion placed on the back of the buffalo, and the left leg is planted on the pedestal. A trident held in the right forehand of the Devī is jabbed into the cushioned back of the fallen buffalo. The back right hand holds a raised sword (*khadga*). The other back hand holds a bell. The demon emerging from the buffalo's body was seized by the goddess by the hair and mount lion mauls the half-emerging man from the hind part of the buffalo. We can see the third eye of the goddess on the centre of the forehead. Ornaments worn by the Devī are different from the earlier discussed sculptures of Mahiṣāsūramardīnī; here we can see the influence of local folk tradition especially in the neck jewellery worn by the goddess and also on the dress. She wears a dress which has vertical studded stripes. The goddess wears a three-pointed crown, generally we found in the hill area especially Kulu district of Himachal Pradesh. She also wear *kuṇḍala* with tassels which touched the shoulder, bracelets, *dhotī* and a girdle with tassels of pearl strings which are very unique. She wears beaded and plain necklaces (*mālās*) and another necklace which is hanging between the breasts of the Devī.

There is another similar image of four-handed Mahiṣāsūramardīnī standing in *pratiyālīḍha* posture. She wears her usual dress and ornaments. This image is badly mutilated.

There are also two images, out of the seven *sapta-mātrikas* are placed in the complex of the temple. An image of goddess Varāhi is shown boar faced. She is seated in *lalitāsana* on her *vāhana* buffalo. She has four hands. She holds a bell and bowl in the left hands and sword and an indistinct object in her right hands. She wears a crown, necklace, armlets, anklets and bracelets. An image of four-armed Kaumārī similarly seated is shown on her mount peacock. Unfortunately, all the iconographic details are worn off. These both images show that there is supremacy of Sakti cult in this region.

The images of the goddess Gaṅgā and Yamunā were made in the Gupta time for the first time.[5] According to *Agni Purāṇa*[6] Gaṅgā should be standing on a crocodile, holding a lotus and a *ghaṭa*. Yamunā should be shown as seated on a tortoise and carrying a *ghaṭa*. The *Viṣṇudharmottara Purāṇa*[7] also states a similar description except for their attributes. A blue lotus should be shown in the hands of Gaṅgā and Yamunā. These are carved in high relief in the true tradition of the Gupta art, instilled with spirituality. The outer walls of the newly constructed temple at Dattnagar (Dattātreya Mahādeva temple), preserve the sculptures of the goddess Gaṅgā and Yamunā. These goddesses wear their usual dress and ornaments. Gaṅgā stands on a crocodile and Yamunā on a tortoise. These images of the goddesses represent the continued tradition of sculpting the Gaṅgā and Yamunā on the doorjambes of the temple from the Gupta period onwards. At Dattnagar they have been reused from some ruined temple, possibly of the *nāgara* style.

A four-handed Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa (Pl. VI) is now in the State Museum Shimla procured from Dattnagar. Viṣṇu seated in *lalitāsana* on a flying Garuḍa shown as a man. It measures 65 cm by 48.5 cm. On the left bent thigh of Viṣṇu is shown Lakṣmī seated with one leg flicked under and other is not visible except fingers of the foot. Lord Viṣṇu throws his left arm around Lakṣmī and holds the conch. Goddess Lakṣmī also kept her right hand on the right shoulder of Viṣṇu. But instead of looking at him, she turned her head to face the viewer or devotees. In the back right and left rear hands he is holding mace and discus respectively while on his left right hand he is holding a tiny lotus. There is eight-petalled lotus halo at the back of his head which is flanked by the other two figures, probably Brahmā and Śiva right and left side of the main deity. Two-handed Garuḍa is depicted supporting the feet of Viṣṇu. Viṣṇu is wearing *kirīṭa-mukuṭa*, *kaṇaphūla*, bracelets, anklets, and armlets. A female devotee is shown in the right corner of pedestal kneeling with devotion.

Another Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa (Pl. VII) astride Garuḍa is placed in the same temple at Dattnagar. It measures 73 cm by 40 cm. He is holding clockwise from the front right hand lotus, mace, disc and conch. He is seated in *lalitāsana* and the right foot resting on the lotus shaped cushion. The left leg is bent and the foot is resting on the hand of the Garuḍa. The deity wears a necklace, bracelets, sacred thread, *vanamālā*, earrings (*kaṇaphūla*). He is also wearing *kirīṭamukuṭa*. Halo at the back is in the form of a full-bloomed double petalled lotus framed within the concentric band. The face of the deity is modelled in oval shape. At the top flanking the both left and right sides of the halo are *gandharvas* or musicians holding *viṇā* in their hands. The image is partially broken from the left side of the pedestal on which the figure of the devotee has weathered out. On the right side of the deity, at the base, there is also a female figure is standing in *sambhaṅga* posture. Lakṣmī is shown seated on the left leg of Viṣṇu. Her body above the waist is in frontal position seeing the viewer and below the waist is in almost profile stretched towards the back. With her right arm she is embracing Viṣṇu and her left arm is placed in the front holding small lotus.

Garuḍa is depicted in anthropomorphic form. This kind of posture and anthropomorphic form of Garuḍa is quite common in the sculptures of Shimla, Nirmand and Karsog

regions. However, the hair-style of the Garuḍa is very different. On the basis of the stylistic characteristics, this image can be placed in the fourteenth century CE and local art idioms are clearly discernible in the facial details.

Another similar depiction of Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa (Pl. VIII) is astride Garuḍa in the same temple at Dattnagar. It measures 65 cm by 37 cm. He is holding clockwise from the front right hand lotus, mace, disc and conch. He is seated in *lalitāsana* and the right foot resting on the lotus-shaped cushion. The left leg is bent and the foot is resting on the head of the Garuḍa. The deity wears a necklace, bracelets, sacred thread, *vanamālā* and earrings. He is also wearing *kirīṭamukuṭa*. Halo at the back is in the form of a full-bloomed lotus framed within the concentric band. The face of the deity is modelled in round shape. At the top of both left and a right side of the halo are Brahmā and Siva. Lakṣmī is shown seated on the left leg of Viṣṇu. Garuḍa is depicted in an anthropomorphic form. At the base, there are male and female *āyudhas* holding some attributes that cannot be ascertained. On the basis of the stylistic characteristics, this image can be placed in the fourteenth-fifteenth centuries CE. A similar four handed Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa (Pl. IX) is placed in the Dattātreya temple at Dattnagar. It measures 37 cm by 24 cm. Viṣṇu seated in *lalitasana* on a flying Garuḍa shown as a man. It seems to be a sculpture of later period.

A sculpture of Umā-Maheśvara (Pl. X) is placed in the niche of the Dattātreya Mahādeva temple at Dattnagar in the Shimla district of Himachal Pradesh. This image is small in size. The image is depicting Śiva-Pārvatī seated on Nandī. The sculpture's iconic details are worn-off. Śiva with his consort Umā is seated on his left bent leg. Lord Śiva is seated in *lalitāsana* in royal ease on his *vāhana* Nandī. His right leg is resting on the lotus cushion. He holds in the back right hand a trident and in his back left a snake. The front right hand is holding a lotus. Both left hands are broken.

The goddess returns his embrace by encircling his shoulder. Śiva wears *jaṭāmukuṭa*, *yajñopavīta*, *vanamālā*, necklace and armlets. The goddess Pārvatī is seated cross-legged and holding lotus in her left hand. She is wearing her usual dress and ornaments such as a tiara, earrings, necklace bangles and anklets. Her hair is tied in the shape of the bun above her head and decorated with *hair ornament*.

Methodology

Field Survey, Qualitative and quantitative both methods has been used.

Analysis

Artistic Style On The Basis Of Chronology

On the basis of the chronology of above-discussed images from Dattātreya Mahādeva temple we can categorized these images into two phases: In the first phase we can see the transitions from the late classical phase to the an early folk phase where artist started to copy the earlier iconography. The eight-armed goddesses (Pls. II, III) wearing her usual ornaments and attributes, three-pointed crown and pot belly lacks the expression and plasticity of the earlier period.

In the Second phase where artist attempts a new interpretation of earlier iconography, for instance a fourteen-fifteenth century image of the Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa (Pls. VI, VII) shows an overall aesthetic degeneration in the features and the expression is clearly visible in this image. The images of Goddesses (Pls. IV, V) are belongs to this phase. Summing up the discussion that the sculptures are continued to be carved in stone and there are numerous pieces known from the various parts of the Sutlej region till medieval period. The features of this image show local development, rather a decline in the influence of the style of the Pratihāra period sculpture in the images of the Sutlej region. This image is contemporary with the temple which is datable to the thirteenth-fourteenth century or even later.

Conclusion

Some of the observed features of the above mentioned images are the following:

1. Worship of the Śakti in form of Mahiṣāsura-mardīnī is popular in the Shimla region of Sutlej valley.
2. Lakṣmī is shown seated on the left leg of Viṣṇu. However, her body above the waist is in frontal position seeing the viewer.
3. Most of the time Garuḍa is depicted in anthropomorphic form, which is quite common in the sculptures of Shimla, Nirmand and Karsog regions. However, the hair-style of the Garuḍa is very different.
4. The shape of the crown of goddess differs from the classical proto-type of north India. The God and goddess wears a three-pointed crown, generally we found in the hill area especially Kulu district of Himachal Pradesh. It is reproduced from local model or the three-pointed crown so typical of Chamba and Kulu is accepted.
5. We can observe a prominent influence of local folk tradition especially on the dress and neck jewellery worn by the god and goddess and also on the dress.
6. We can notice the third eye of the goddess similar to *mohrās* which is very popular in this region on the centre of the forehead.
7. It lacks the earlier round modelling; images are depicted as elongated face with high forehead, v-shaped smile, prominent chin, slim waist and more ornamentation.
8. Goddesses (Pls. II, III, IV) wearing long dress which marked with vertical and horizontal studded loops.
9. We can notice the third eye of the goddess similar to *mohrā* which is very popular in this region on the centre of the forehead.

10. The back side of the trident of the Mahiṣāsūramardīnī (Pl.VI) is decorated with *āmalaka*.

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6. *Agni Purāṇa*, 50, 17.
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Pl. I: Three metal sculptures, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. II: Mahiṣāsura mardini, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla

Pl. III, Mahiṣāsura mardini, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. IV, Mahiṣāsūramardīnī, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. V: Mahiṣāsūramardīnī, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

PI. VI: Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

PI. VII: Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. VIII: Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. IX: Lakṣmī-Nārāyaṇa Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.

Pl. X: Umā-Maheśvara, Dattātreya Mahādeva Temple, Dattnagar, Shimla.